

NOTES

Complexes of Copper(II) with the Disulphides of Thiosalicylic Acid

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THE disulphides of thiosalicylic acid differ from the sulphides in having a restriction in freedom of rotation about the S—S bond amounting to 10–20 kcal. This is explained by the fact that the disulphide bond may, in its ground state, have some double bond character resulting from the interactions of electrons in the p-orbitals of one sulphur atom with the d-orbital of the adjacent sulphur atom. Further, there may be a repulsion between the adjacent lone-pairs of p-electrons¹. In the Cu^{II}-thiosalicylic acid (HSC₆H₄COOH) system, the formation of Cu^I(SC₆H₄COOH) and the 2-2'-disulphide (I) was observed². The biochemical importance of the mercaptide group in the Cu^{II}-thiol system has been emphasised^{3,4}.

I

(2-2'-Disulphide of thiosalicylic acid)

II

(4-4'-Disulphide of thiosalicylic acid)

Experimental

2-2'-Disulphide (I) was prepared by oxidising commercially available thiosalicylic acid. A suspension of thiosalicylic acid (10 g) in water was treated with CuSO₄·5H₂O (2 g) and acidified with 4 N HCl (2 ml). The mixture was stirred for ~1 h and filtered. The precipitate was recrystallised (95%) from acetone.

4-4'-Disulphide (II) was prepared starting from *p*-aminobenzoic acid. *p*-Aminobenzoic acid (10 g) was treated with concentrated HCl (25 ml). The mixture was cooled to -5° in salt-ice freezing mixture and diazotised by adding an ice-cold solution of NaNO₂ (6 g in 15 ml water). To a boiling solution of Na₂S (4 g in 20 ml water), were added powdered sulphur (2.5 g) and NaOH (3 g). The

mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and the diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid was added in small quantities over a period of 2 h. The precipitate was filtered and dissolved in a solution of Na₂CO₃ when only the 4-4'-isomer went into solution. The solution was acidified with HCl and the 4-4'-isomer got precipitated. The isomer was recrystallised (25%) from acetone.

Cu^{II}-(2-2'-RSSR)Cl₂·H₂O (1): CuSO₄·5H₂O (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in NH₃—NH₄Cl buffer (50 ml) of pH 9.25. The 2-2'-isomer (1.53 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in the buffer (20 ml). The CuSO₄ solution was added to the ligand solution and the mixture stirred for ~5 min. On acidification with 1 : 1 HCl, the dark brown complex precipitated at pH 6.81. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and then with acetone, and dried in vacuum.

Cu^{II}-(2-2'-RSSR)(OOCCH₃)₂·2H₂O (2): CuSO₄·5H₂O (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in NaOAc—HOAc buffer (30 ml). The 2-2'-isomer (3.06 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in the buffer (30 ml). The Cu^{II} solution was added to the ligand solution and stirred for 10 h. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and finally with acetone and dried in vacuum.

Cu^{II}-(2-2'-RSSR)₂(OH)₂·2H₂O (3): The method of preparation is the same as for (2), but for the metal to ligand ratio, 2 : 1.

Cu^{II}-(2-2'-RSSR)·H₂O (4): The 2-2'-isomer (1.53 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of NaOH and then added an aqueous solution of CuSO₄·5H₂O (2.49 g, 0.01 mol). The green precipitate was washed with water and finally with acetone and dried in vacuum.

Cu^{II}-(4-4'-RSSR)·H₂O (5): The 4-4'-isomer (3.06 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of NaOH and to it then added an aqueous solution of CuSO₄·5H₂O (2.49 g, 0.01 mol, 15 ml). The pale green precipitate was filtered, washed with water and finally with acetone and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The ν_{Cu-O} of monocarboxylate complexes generally occurs⁵ in the range 350–480 cm⁻¹. In all the complexes, absorptions around 410 cm⁻¹ (Cu—O) were noticed. The oxygen of the carboxylic acid alone ligates with the copper. The ν_{O-H} peaks are prominently observed in the range 3100–3600 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of water.

The magnetic moments of complexes 4 and 5 are normal as expected for one unpaired electron^{6,7}.

Other complexes have subnormal μ_{eff} values (1.4 to 1.5 B.M.) suggesting Cu—Cu interaction⁹. This is due to the extent of bonding; the bonding being strongest when there is no unpaired electron, *i.e.* when the magnetic moment is zero. If it is 1.73 B.M., there is no interaction of Cu—Cu bonding. The intermediate values of 1.4–1.5 in the case of 1–3 complexes suggest the mixing up of the electrons.

The powder pattern studies show that all the complexes are amorphous.

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Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Dioxouranium(II) Complexes of Thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES and their metal complexes are well known for their pharmacological importance^{1–6}. Extensive studies on 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide derivative metal ion complexes have been reported^{7–9}. The present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of thiophene-2-aldehyde-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (TAPTSC) and its metal complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO^{II}.

Experimental

Synthesis of TAPTSC: 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (Fluka) (8.35 g) dissolved in ethanol (50 cm³) was gradually added to thiophene-2-aldehyde (Fluka) (4.6 cm³) mixed in ethanol (30 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h. A white crystalline solid separated on cooling, was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether, and dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure. TAPTSC (85%), thus obtained, was insoluble in hot water but soluble in hot ethanol.

Synthesis of metal complexes of TAPTSC: To the aqueous ethanolic solution (0.004 mol) of metal acetates (AnalaR) TAPTSC (0.008 mol) dissolved in hot ethanol (60 cm³) was gradually added with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for ~1 h and left overnight. Coloured solids separated were filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether and dried in air. The metal complexes of TAPTSC (80%) were air-stable, coloured solids and insoluble in hot water but soluble in hot ethanol. The purity of the TAPTSC and its complexes was checked by tlc, m.p./decomp. temp. and also microanalysis.

Infrared spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Beckman—Aculab 10 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm⁻¹. Diffuse reflectance spectra were obtained in the range 200–1 000 nm on a Carl—Zeiss VSU-22 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at ~303 K by Gouy's method. T.G. data were recorded by heating the complexes in air upto 800° at the rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 2 metal—ligand stoichiometry. μ_{eff} value of 4.46 B.M. of the paramagnetic Co^{II} complex corresponds to three unpaired electrons and lies within the range reported for tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes^{10–12}. The diffuse reflectance spectra of Co^{II}-TAPTSC exhibit two bands, the one intense band at 17 094 cm⁻¹ and the other weak band at 19 203 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) confirming spin-free tetrahedral geometry around the Co^{II} ion^{11–13}.

The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic indicating the formation of a spin paired, square-planar geometry around Ni^{II} in the complex^{14–16}, as was evident from one intense broad band at 24 390 cm⁻¹ in the diffuse reflectance spectra and could be assigned to transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g. The Cu^{II} complex is paramagnetic (μ_{eff} = 1.94 B.M.) for one unpaired electron¹⁷. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows one broad band at 23 255 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transition ²B_{1g} → ²E_g arising from a square-planar geometry^{16–18}. Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO^{II} complexes with TAPTSC are all diamagnetic.

The ir spectra of TAPTSC shows characteristic^{19–24} bands at 1 550 (N—C—N), 1 430 (C=S) and 1 310 cm⁻¹ (NH—C=S) arising from the thione form of the ligand (I) in the solid state. This is further supported by the presence of a C=S band at 810 cm⁻¹.

(I)